

Supporting information for

A highly sensitive ratiometric optical thermometer based on Sr₂MgWO₆ double perovskite doped with Dy³⁺

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Table S1. The chromaticity coordinates (x,y) of Sr₂MgWO₆:xDy³⁺, xLi⁺ (x = 0, 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7%) upon 266 nm excitation at room temperature

Sample	CIE (x, y)
SMW host	(0.211, 0.269)
SMW:0.1%Dy ³⁺	(0.382, 0.387)
SMW:0.5%Dy ³⁺	(0.456, 0.453)
SMW:1%Dy ³⁺	(0.445, 0.449)
SMW:3%Dy ³⁺	(0.480, 0.471)
SMW:5%Dy ³⁺	(0.463, 0.462)
SMW:7%Dy ³⁺	(0.426, 0.444)

Figure S1. Temperature-dependent emission spectra of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:3\%\text{Dy}^{3+}, 3\%\text{Li}^+$ excited at 266 nm, from 80 – 673 K. Inset: Integrated emission intensity as a function of temperature.

Table S2. The parameters of decay profiles of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:x\text{Dy}^{3+}, x\text{Li}^+$ ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7\%$) monitored at 574 nm, excited at 266 nm wavelength at room temperature

x	A_1	τ_1 (s)	A_2	τ_2 (s)	τ_{avg} (μs)
0.1%	0.7086	4.54E-05	0.31843	1.92E-04	141.2
0.5%	0.41725	4.89E-05	0.53019	1.99E-04	174.8
1%	0.61061	4.62E-05	0.42445	1.80E-04	143.9
3%	0.44167	5.54E-05	0.42834	2.00E-04	167.9
5%	0.50303	4.13E-05	0.42951	1.70E-04	141.2
7%	0.72852	4.78E-05	0.21378	1.73E-04	112.3

Figure S2. Arrhenius plot of the temperature dependence of the emission intensity of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:3\%\text{Dy}^{3+}, 3\%\text{Li}^+$

Figure S3. 80 K emission spectra of $\text{Sr}_2\text{MgWO}_6:x\%\text{Dy}^{3+}, x\%\text{Li}^+$ ($x = 0.1, 0.5, 1, 3, 5, 7\%$) excited at $\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 266 \text{ nm}$

Figure S4. a) Temperature - dependent emission spectra of Sr₂MgWO₆:5%Dy³⁺, 5%Li⁺ ($\lambda_{exc} = 266$ nm) in the range of 80 - 293 K; b) Normalized emission intensity of the host and Dy³⁺ transitions as a function of temperature

Figure S5. a) Temperature - dependent emission spectra of Sr₂MgWO₆:7%Dy³⁺, 7%Li⁺ ($\lambda_{exc} = 266$ nm) in the range of 80 - 293 K; b) Normalized emission intensity of the host and Dy³⁺ transitions as a function of temperature

Figure S6. (a-c) FIRs of thermally uncoupled levels and its fitting curves (black lines); (d-f) Absolute sensitivities, S_a (K^{-1}) of SMW: $x\%Dy^{3+}$, $x\%Li^+$ where $x = 3\%$, 5% , 7% in the range of 80 - 293 K

Figure S7. (a-c) FIRs of thermally coupled levels and its fitting curves (red lines); (d-f) Absolute sensitivities, S_a (K^{-1}) of SMW: $x\%Dy^{3+}$, $x\%Li^+$ ($x = 3\%$, 5% , 7%), respectively in the range of 293 - 593 K

Figure S8. Repeatability of FIR₃₁ at 80 K and 173 K during 6 consecutive heating/cooling cycles of Sr₂MgWO₆: 3%Dy³⁺, 3%Li⁺